

PCR, ANAEROBIC BACTERIA, MAXILLOFACIAL INFLAMMATION, MICROBIOCENOSIS, REAL-TIME PCR, MOLECULAR DIAGNOSTICS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18832435>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 26th February 2026

Accepted: 27th February 2026

Online: 28th February 2026

KEYWORDS

PCR, anaerobic bacteria,
maxillofacial inflammation,
microbiocenosis, real-time PCR,
molecular diagnostics

ABSTRACT

In recent years, traditional microbiological diagnostic methods for inflammatory diseases have been supplemented by molecular genetic technologies. Polymerase chain reaction (PCR), developed in the mid-1980s, enables rapid DNA amplification and allows identification of microorganisms without isolation of pure cultures. This study aimed to improve the etiological diagnosis of inflammatory diseases of the maxillofacial region using real-time PCR. The results demonstrated frequent detection of anaerobic pathogens and significant disruption of the natural microbiocenosis with the predominance of opportunistic flora. Real-time PCR proved to be a highly informative and specific method for detecting difficult-to-cultivate anaerobic bacteria.

Introduction. Conventional microbiological diagnostic methods for inflammatory diseases are increasingly complemented by molecular genetic technologies. The development of polymerase chain reaction (PCR) in the mid-1980s enabled artificial amplification of DNA sequences and significantly improved laboratory diagnostics. PCR allows detection and identification of microorganisms without the need for pure culture isolation, which is particularly important for difficult-to-cultivate anaerobic bacteria. Inflammatory diseases of the maxillofacial region are often associated with polymicrobial anaerobic infections. Rapid and accurate etiological identification is essential for effective treatment and prevention of complications.

Aim of the Study. To improve the etiological diagnosis of inflammatory diseases of the maxillofacial region using real-time PCR technology.

Materials and Methods. Biological material was obtained from 47 patients (37 males and 10 females). Real-time PCR diagnostics were used to detect genetic material of selected difficult-to-cultivate anaerobic bacteria. In all patients, PCR real-time confirmed the presence of genetic material corresponding to at least 10^5 CFU/mL of the detected microorganism. Microbiological analysis included evaluation of monocultures and microbial associations isolated from wound exudates. Quantitative bacterial contamination ranged from 10^6 to 10^8 CFU.

Results. The study demonstrated frequent isolation of anaerobic pathogens in pure culture among most examined patients. Disruption of the natural microbiocenosis with the appearance of opportunistic microflora was observed:

- Coccal flora predominated in 27 patients (57.4%)
- Streptococcus spp. were detected in 11 patients (40.7%)
- Staphylococcus spp. in 5 patients (18.5%)
- Peptostreptococcus spp. in 4 patients (14.8%)

Monoculture was isolated from wound exudate in 21 cases (44.6%), while microbial associations were detected in 26 cases (55.3%).

Genetic material in diagnostically significant titers was most frequently identified in:

- Bacteroides caccae (29% of patients)
- Porphyromonas endodontalis (29%)
- A similar trend was observed for Fusobacterium nucleatum

Discussion. The findings confirm that anaerobic pathogens play a major role in inflammatory diseases of the maxillofacial region. Real-time PCR demonstrated high sensitivity and specificity in detecting difficult-to-cultivate microorganisms. The predominance of microbial associations indicates the polymicrobial nature of purulent maxillofacial infections. Disruption of normal microbiocenosis contributes to disease progression. The local clinical status of a purulent wound is a leading indicator of the patient's overall condition and rehabilitation process. The local clinical status of a purulent wound is a leading indicator of the patient's overall condition and rehabilitation process. Therefore, development of adequate rapid monitoring methods for diagnosis and dynamic observation is essential, as well as new pathogenetically justified treatment strategies, especially targeting etiological factors.

Conclusion. Real-time PCR is a highly informative and specific method for detecting anaerobic pathogens in inflammatory diseases of the maxillofacial region. The method significantly improves etiological diagnostics and may contribute to more targeted and effective therapeutic approaches.

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